

The Impact Of Demographic Factors On Delinquency Prone Adolescents

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Abstract

Adolescence is a critical developmental stage characterized by significant physical, emotional, and social changes. During this period, individuals are particularly susceptible to various influences that can impact their behavior and adjustment. Delinquency, or involvement in antisocial and criminal activities, is a concern that affects many adolescents, posing significant challenges for families, schools, and communities. Demographic factors such as gender, socio economic status and the urban-rural divide play a crucial role in shaping the experiences and behaviors of delinquency-prone adolescents. Understanding these factors is essential for developing targeted interventions and prevention strategies. The current study examined the impact of demographic factors on delinquency prone adolescents of district Sahibzada Ajit Singh Nagar(Punjab).228 delinquency prone adolescents (Boys and Girls) from rural and urban schools were selected for the study. The delinquency proneness scale prepared by Dr.Kamini Sehgal was used to collect data. Statistical tools like, means, standard deviations and t-scores were used to obtain results. The data showed no significant results in relation to demographic factors and adolescent delinquency proneness.

Keywords Adolescents, Delinquency, Proneness, Demographic Factors.

Introduction

In the twenty-first century, there has been tremendous progress in all areas of human endeavor. However, because of the tremendous progress made in every sector, our adolescents are straying off their course. They are engaged in antisocial behavior.

In general, adolescence is the time when a person is neither a child nor an adult. This is a time of great change, tremendous expansion, and, most importantly, human existence. Puberty marks the start of this phase, and growth accession marks its conclusion. It arises in childhood and combines with maturity. It can be viewed as a transfer from the early years to adulthood in a number of domains, including the physical, social, intellectual, and emotional. This phase is seen as critical in numerous ways. A slight tendency in any kind has the power to diverge them. Rapid industrialization and urbanization that follows, the rise in schooling, the breakup of the joint family unit, the use of cell phones, and media exposure have prevented a portion of the young people worldwide from adapting to the rapidly changing society in a stable and healthy way. Due to the embrace of western culture, the socialization process has changed, increasing the risk of delinquency among our young people.

Juvenile Delinquency

When an adolescent engages in behaviors that are considered unacceptable by society, such as stealing, assaulting, or participating in sexual offences, they are considered delinquents. The term "delinquere," which is made up of the words "de," which means "away," and "linquere," which means "to leave," or "to abandon," is from where the word "delinquency" originates.

In general, delinquency can be defined as "falling away" from normal behavior or behavior that is socially unacceptable. Legally speaking, this means that certain antisocial behavior

violations committed by teenagers, if committed by an adult, would be regarded as crimes and subject to legal punishment. Generally delinquency is learned behavior rather than an anomaly.

-According to Kvaraceous and Miller, "Delinquent behavior is defined as conduct by teenagers that breaches standards of a specific social institution frequently enough and/or seriously enough to give rise to a solid basis for legal action against the behavior of an individual or group."

-Cole "A person who violates socially acceptable norms of behavior because their ego is bent on instant gratification and their conscience is weak" is considered a delinquent.

-According to Muthuswamy (1999) ,delinquent behavior is the antisocial behavior of youngsters who have run afoul of the law.

-According to Travis Hirschi (1969), "The delinquency is defined by acts, the detection of which is thought to result in punishment of the person committing them by agents of the larger society."

-Dictionary of Education, A person who disobeys the rules, disobeys social standards, violates the law, or causes indiscipline in a school or other institution is considered a delinquent. It is believed that his unethical behavior is not severe enough to make him a culprit. Juvenile courts investigate his unlawful actions.

Delinquency Proneness

The risk of a teenager committing an anti-social behavior is known as delinquency proneness. The likelihood that teenagers may turn criminals if they are exposed to opportunities and temptations that are reasonably commonplace. This is known as delinquency proneness. Therefore, it is the departure from the recognized norms of a society's culture or the applicable laws.

Statement of the problem

Children are born innocent and free from malice; it is society's influence that shapes them and can inculcate crime in them This study seeks to fill the gap in understanding the society's influence through, complex relation between gender, urban-rural context and adolescent delinquency. By examining these interactions, the research aims to provide insights that can inform more effective and context-specific prevention and intervention strategies, ultimately, reducing delinquent behavior and promoting better adjustment and outcomes for all adolescents.

Objective of study

The aim of study was to examine' "The impact of demographic factors on Delinquency Prone Adolescents"

1. To explore the significance of difference in delinquency proneness of boys and girls.
2. To explore the significance of difference in delinquency proneness of adolescents from rural and urban schools.

Hypothesis

1. There is no significant difference in delinquency proneness of boys and girls.
2. There is no significant difference in delinquency proneness of adolescents from rural and urban schools.

Review of Literature

Gender Differences in Delinquency

Research consistently shows significant gender differences in delinquent behavior

1. Moffitt (1993) proposed that males are more likely to exhibit life-course-persistent antisocial behavior, while females are often limited to adolescence-limited delinquency.
2. There are no gender differences on the Jessness measures of delinquent proneness, according to Mohan and Nalwa (1992)

3. Gulati and Dutta (2004) examined the mental health profiles of 245 rural teenagers (12 to 16 years old) who were selected from impoverished but stable households. They discovered that while anxiety and depression were more common in girls, delinquency was the main issue for males.
4. According to Devi and Mayuri's (2001) analysed the psychological profile of juvenile offenders and found that there are notable differences between males and females in terms of their sensitivity, maturity, and guilt proneness.
5. Chesney-Lind and Sheldon (2004) highlighted that societal expectations and gender socialization play a critical role in shaping delinquent behavior. Boys are often socialized to be aggressive and dominant, which can lead to higher rates of overt delinquency. In contrast, girls may express their delinquency through relational aggression and are more likely to be influenced by victimization and trauma.
6. Chauhan (2013), observed that female students had better adjustment in higher secondary schools as compared to males.
7. Panth ,Chaurasia, and Gupta(2015), found differences in emotional maturity and adjustment between genders, highlighting the need for gender sensitive approaches to delinquency prevention and intervention

Urban-Rural Differences in Delinquency

The urban-rural divide also significantly impacts adolescent delinquency.

1. Welsh, Greene, and Jenkins (1999) noted that urban areas tend to have higher rates of delinquency due to factors such as greater population density, socioeconomic disparities, and increased exposure to crime. Urban adolescents often face more opportunities and peer pressure to engage in delinquent activities. In contrast, rural areas, while generally exhibiting lower overall delinquency rates, present unique challenges.
2. According to Donnermeyer and DeKeseredy (2014), rural adolescents may experience isolation, limited access to recreational activities, and a lack of anonymity, which can contribute to delinquent behavior. Additionally, rural communities may have fewer resources for addressing delinquency, such as counseling services and extracurricular programs.
3. According to Acchorn (1955), the environment plays a role as a trigger for the development of delinquency.
4. Losen and Skiba (2010), shed light on the role of school discipline policies and the prevalence of school disorder in shaping delinquent behavior among students.

Intersection of Gender and Urban-Rural Context

The intersection of gender and the urban-rural context creates distinct patterns of delinquency.

1. Estrada and Nilsson (2015) found that while boys in both urban and rural settings are more likely to engage in delinquent behavior, the types of delinquency and the influencing factors differ. Urban boys often face peer-related pressures and opportunities for gang involvement, while rural boys may be influenced by family dynamics and community isolation. For girls, the urban-rural context also plays a significant role. Urban girls may encounter higher risks of sexual exploitation and relational aggression, while rural girls might struggle with limited social networks and support systems.
2. Yellaiah (2012), found no significant differences in adjustment and academic achievement based on gender, school type, or rural/urban location.
3. According to a study by Smith et.al. (2020), cyber bullying and online harassment are significant issues among urban adolescents ,who have greater access to digital devices and social media platforms.
4. Makwana and Kaji (2014), observed that social adjustment issues are particularly pronounced for rural girls, who may find it challenging to navigate social relationships in small, close-knit communities.

Socioeconomic Factors

Socioeconomic status is another critical demographic factor influencing delinquency. Lower socioeconomic conditions, often more prevalent in urban areas, can exacerbate the risk of delinquency by limiting access to education, employment, and recreational opportunities.

1. Farrington (1998) demonstrated that socioeconomic disadvantage is a significant predictor of both childhood aggression and later-life criminal behavior.
2. According to Uche's (1994) research, children who have well-off and well-educated parents of high social standing receive excellent private education and are less likely to engage in criminal activity than their counterparts from lower socioeconomic backgrounds.

In rural settings, economic challenges such as unemployment and underemployment can also contribute to delinquency. Rural adolescents from low-income families may engage in delinquent acts as a means of coping with economic stress or due to a lack of structured activities and opportunities.

Sampling

In the current study, descriptive method was used to examine the impact of demographic factors on delinquency prone adolescent boys of District Sahibzada Ajit Singh Nagar. A sample was comprised of

228 adolescents, enrolled in 10+1 classes at government schools in the Sahibzada Ajit Singh Nagar, District of Punjab. The Government schools from Rural as well as Urban areas were selected using the basic random sampling approach.

Tools Used 1. Delinquency Proneness Scale developed by Dr. Kamini Sehgal was used in the study. The range of scores on this scale was 50-250. Adolescents with high scores on this scale are significantly more likely to exhibit delinquency prone behaviors.
2. T-test was used to find the level of significance.

Result and Discussion

Table 1: Difference between Delinquency Proneness of adolescent Boys and Girls.

Area	N	Mean	S.D.	t-ratio	Level of Significance
Boys	98	87.77	33.33		
				0.1226	N.S. (0.5)
Girls	130	87.38	26.98		

Note:

N - Number

N.S. - Not Significant

S.D. - Standard deviation

Figure :1

The mean value of boys is 87.77 and mean value of girls is 87.38 and Standard Deviation value of boys is 33.33 and girls is 26.98. The calculated t value is 0.1226 is not significant at.05 level of confidence.

- It indicates that no significant difference exists in delinquency proneness among adolescent boys and girls. Hence the hypothesis that there is no significant difference in delinquency proneness of adolescent boys and girls is accepted.

Table 2: Difference between the Delinquency Proneness of Adolescents from schools of Urban and Rural areas.

Area	N	Mean	S.D.	t-ratio	Level of Significance
Rural	94	86.02	40.63		
				0.6451	N.S. (0.5)
Urban	134	88.61	18.94		

Note:

N - Number

N.S. - Not Significant

S.D. - Standard deviation

Figure:2

The mean value of adolescents from rural schools is 86.02 and mean value of urban adolescents is 88.61 and Standard Deviation value of rural adolescents is 40.63 and urban adolescents is 18.94. The calculated t-value is 0.6451 is not significant at .05 level of confidence.

It indicates that there is no significant difference in delinquency proneness among students studying in rural area schools and urban area schools. Hence the hypothesis that there is no significant difference in delinquency proneness of adolescents from rural and urban schools is accepted.

Conclusion

The findings revealed no significant differences in delinquency proneness between boys and girls or between adolescents from rural and urban school. The current review of literature shows significant gender differences in delinquent behavior. Literature also shows that urban rural divide significantly impacts an adolescent delinquency. So understanding the impact of demographic factors such as gender and urban-rural divide on delinquency-prone adolescents is essential for developing effective prevention and intervention strategies. Further research is necessary to explore these dynamics in greater detail and to identify best practices for addressing delinquency among diverse adolescent population.

Suggestions for the future Study

1. Provide counseling and create programs that cater to the unique needs of both boys and girls, ensuring that both receive the appropriate emotional and psychological support. For boys, focus on reducing overt aggression and peer pressure, while for girls emphasize relational aggression and coping mechanism for trauma and victimization
2. Implement community-based programs that offer safe recreational activities, mentorship,

and gang prevention initiatives to reduce the lure of delinquent behavior among adolescents.

3. Encourage parental involvement through family counseling, parenting workshops, and support networks that strengthen family bonds, and improve communication.

4. Provide quality education through vocational courses for adolescents in both urban and rural areas, ensuring that all students have the opportunity to succeed academically and professionally.

References

1. Acchorn, (1955) *Wayward Youth* New York:Meridion Books.
2. Chesney-Lind, M., & Sheldon, R. G. (2004). *Girls, delinquency, and juvenile justice*. Wadsworth Publishing.
3. Cole, L.(1956).*Psychology of Adolescence*.New York;Rinchart and company, Inc.
4. Devi, U.L. &Mayuri, K.(2001).*Personality profile of adolescent delinquents*.*Journal of Community Guidance and Research*, 18(2), pp157-171
5. Donnermeyer, J. F., & DeKeseredy, W. S. (2014). *Rural criminology*. Routledge.
6. Doran, B. J., & Fawcett, K. (2019). *The influence of urbanization on adolescent delinquency*. *Journal of Urban Studies*, 56(7), 1342-1360.
7. Estrada, F., & Nilsson, A. (2018). *Family dynamics and adolescent delinquency: The impact of parental involvement*. *Journal of Family Psychology*, 32(5), 623-632.
8. Gulati, J.K.and Dutta, J(2004).*Mental Health profile of Rural Adolescents Living in Persistent Economic Hardship*. *Man in India*, 84(1, 2).pp113-121.Retrieved from <http://shodhganga.inflibnet.ac.in/bitstream/10603/13752/>
9. Hirchi, T.(1969).*Causes of Delinquency*.Berkley and Los Angeles:University of California Presss.
10. Kearney, M. S., Harris, B. H., & Jácome, E. (2020). *The role of gender and urban-rural context in adolescent delinquency*. *National Bureau of Economic Research*.
11. Kvaraceous, W.C.&Miller, W.B.(1954).*Delinquent Behaviour, Culture and Individuals*.Washington;National Education Association.
12. Makwana, L., & Kaji, S. (2014). *Adjustment problems of rural and urban adolescents*. *Indian Journal of Psychological Medicine*, 36(3), 270-273.
13. Moffitt, T.E.(1993).*Adolescence- limited and life-course-persistent antisocial behavior: A developmental taxonomy*. *Psychological Review*, 100(4), 674-701.
14. Mohan, V. & Nalwa, K. (1992). *Delinquency Proneness as related to deprivation*.*Indian Journal of Criminology*. 20(2), 93-98.
15. Nagarathnamma(1992).*Indian Journal of Psychology*.67, (1+2), 17-21.
16. Pruitt, L. R., Burdick-Will, J., & Legewie, J. (2017). *Neighborhood violence and adolescent delinquency*. *American Journal of Sociology*, 123(1), 178-218.
17. Reardon, S. F., Weathers, E. S., & Fahle, E. (2019). *The socioeconomic determinants of adolescent delinquency*. *Educational Researcher*, 48(3), 191-206.
18. Schwartz, D., Lansford, J. E., Dodge, K. A., Pettit, G. S., & Bates, J. E. (2019). *Peer influence and adolescent delinquency*. *Journal of Youth and Adolescence*, 48(5), 851-865.
19. Sehgal, kamini., (2018).*Delinquency proneness scale*
20. Sehgal, K. & Sawhney, S.(2019) *Delinquency Proneness among Adolescents in Relation to Demographic Variables*. *Shrinkhla Ek Shodhparak Vaicharik Patrika*.
21. Sjöberg, S., & Lindberg, S. (2018).*Gender differences in peer influence and delinquency*. *Criminal Justice and Behavior*, 45(8), 1157-1176.
22. Smith, P. K., Mahdavi, J., & Carvalho, M. (2020). *Cyber bullying and adolescent delinquency*. *Journal of Adolescent Health*, 56(1), 65-70.
23. Welsh, W. N., Greene, J. R., & Jenkins, P. H. (1999). *School disorder and delinquency*. *Journal of School Violence*, 18(2), 121-140.
24. Wilkinson, R. G., & Pickett, K. E. (2017). *Economic inequality and social dysfunction: The rural context*. *Rural Sociology*, 82(1), 75-97.

Websites

1. <http://www.sciencepub.net/report>
2. <http://www.ijfmr.com>